

Development of Event-Biasing Techniques for Variance Reduction in Hydrogenous Shielding Simulations

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803868

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ABSTRACT

The Monte Carlo method is widely used in reactor design and radiation shielding analysis. However, in deep-penetration problems, Monte Carlo transport simulations often suffer from insufficient particle histories in regions of interest, large statistical variances, and slow convergence. The local variance reduction (LVR) technique dynamically adjusts sampling probabilities and particle weights at each collision or transport event to improve computational efficiency. In this study, a novel event-biased weighting method based on path length and hydrogen collision probability is proposed for variance reduction in shielding calculations. The method is implemented in the open-source Monte Carlo code OpenMC, and benchmark results demonstrate that it can significantly extend particle penetration paths and reduce statistical variance in deep-penetration simulations.

Keywords: Monte Carlo; Deep penetration problem; Variance reduction method; Event-Biasing

1. INTRODUCTION

The pursuit of variance reduction in Monte Carlo particle transport dates back to the seminal work of Kahn and Marshall [1], who laid the statistical groundwork for enhancing sampling efficiency. Over subsequent decades, these methods transitioned from general mathematical heuristics to specialized transport-coupled algorithms, with the definitive framework established by Lux and Koblinger [2] marking the maturation of modern variance reduction systems. The fixed-source Monte Carlo transport method plays a crucial role in evaluating shielding performance, calculating dose distributions, and estimating detector responses. However, when strong absorption or material attenuation exists between the source and the detector or tally region—commonly referred to as the Deep Penetration problem—the number of significant particle histories becomes extremely small. As a result, shielding calculations suffer from large variances, slow convergence, and poor computational efficiency. Developing effective Variance Reduction (VR) techniques has therefore become the key to improving the efficiency of Monte Carlo simulations [3].

Global Variance Reduction (GVR) methods optimize particle sampling on a system-wide scale by constructing global importance maps or weight windows [4]. In contrast, Local Variance Reduction (LVR) methods dynamically adjust the sampling probability and particle weight during each collision or transport event, optimizing local particle behavior [5]. Typical event-biasing techniques include survival biasing, reaction channel biasing, and scattering angle biasing [6], which improve statistical efficiency at the particle-trajectory level and serve as effective tools for high-accuracy shielding and deep-penetration analyses.

In reactor physics design, hydrogen atoms, with their neutron-like mass and large scattering cross sections, cause strong moderation of fast neutrons, leading to rapid thermalization and absorption. This makes hydrogen both an essential moderator and a “double-edged sword” in deep-penetration simulations, posing significant challenges to shielding calculations. Despite extensive research on VR techniques, studies focusing on microscopic event-biasing mechanisms in particle survival processes remain limited. Therefore, this study proposes a weighted local event-biasing method based on path-

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length biasing and hydrogen collision probability biasing, specifically designed for variance reduction in shielding calculations. The method is implemented and verified in the open-source continuous-energy Monte Carlo code OpenMC [7].

2. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the fundamental principles of the proposed biasing approach, as well as the details of its implementation in OpenMC.

2.1. Conventional Implicit Capture Weighting Method

As discussed in the Introduction, among the existing variance reduction (VR) techniques, the survival biasing method is commonly implemented through the implicit capture weighting scheme. In this approach, a particle undergoing an absorption reaction is not terminated; instead, it continues to transport with a reduced weight. The corresponding weight adjustment at each collision node can be expressed as follows:

$$w' = w \cdot \frac{\Sigma_s^A(E)}{\Sigma_t^A(E)} \quad (1)$$

This method still presents certain physical limitations and room for further generalization. From a first-principles perspective, it may lead to a “spurious over-survival phenomenon”, manifested in the following aspects:

- Uncorrected free path: In a system where only scattering reactions are explicitly considered, the sampled path length is still based on the total cross section Σ_t , neglecting the real suppressive effect of absorption on particle transport.
- Static weight adjustment: The survival probability is fixed, lacking adaptive correction during transport.
- Decoupled reaction mechanisms: The complete detachment of the absorption process causes deviations to propagate, thereby reducing the effectiveness of variance control.

2.2. Variance Reduction Technique Based on Path-Length Biasing

In the path-length biasing technique, the total cross section can be replaced by a smaller quantity, such as the scattering cross section, thereby extending the particle’s mean free path and allowing it to accumulate more transport information.

2.2.1. Sampling Bias and Weight Adjustment

When the free-flight distance l is sampled using the scattering cross section Σ_s instead of the total cross section Σ_t , the biased probability density function P_{survival} can be expressed as:

$$P_{\text{survival}}(l) = \Sigma_s e^{-\Sigma_s l} \quad (2)$$

For the biased probability density function, the corresponding sampled path length with random numbers ξ increases to:

$$s(\xi, \vec{r}, E) = -\frac{1}{\Sigma_s(\vec{r}, E)} \ln(\xi) \quad (3)$$

An additional weight factor is introduced to preserve the unbiasedness of the transport equation:

$$w \cdot P_{\text{true}}(d) \cdot \Sigma_t = w' \cdot P_{\text{biased}}(d) \Sigma_s \quad (4)$$

which leads to the relation:

$$w' = w \cdot e^{-\Sigma_a l} \cdot \frac{\Sigma_t}{\Sigma_s} \quad (5)$$

Where Σ_a is the absorption cross section of the current material. In the real transport process, the mean survival path of a particle l is the inverse of the macroscopic cross section, as expressed:

$$\langle l \rangle = \int_0^\infty x \Sigma_t e^{-\Sigma_t x} dx = \frac{1}{\Sigma_t} \quad (6)$$

When the scattering cross section is used for biasing and the corresponding weight correction is applied as described above, the statistical estimator remains unbiased—that is, the expected value remains invariant:

$$E[w' \cdot f(s')] = E[w \cdot f(s)] \quad (7)$$

where $f(s)$ denotes any trajectory-dependent physical quantity.

Since the path length has been artificially extended, continuing to use the Collision Flux Estimator (CFE) would violate the unbiasedness condition. Therefore, the Track Length Estimator (TLE) should be adopted instead, as expressed in Eq. (8). Σ_r expresses the response cross section for the reaction rate calculation.

$$R = \frac{1}{W} \sum_{i \in C} w_i l_i \Sigma_r \quad (8)$$

2.2.2. Statistical Correction of Tally Counters

In conventional unbiased Monte Carlo transport, the particle path length follows:

$$f_t(l) = \Sigma_t e^{-\Sigma_t l} \quad (9)$$

The particle weight decreases linearly (i.e., uniformly) along its geometrical trajectory. Therefore, when the mesh tally estimator is used to compute geometry-based length-weighted integrals, the path can be directly segmented according to geometric divisions.

When the scattering cross section is instead used for sampling, the actual survival probability of the particle is governed by the absorption cross section Σ_a , as given in Eq. (10).

$$P_{survival}(l) = e^{-\Sigma_a l} \quad (10)$$

After biasing, within each scored MeshFilter, the particle's contribution is no longer uniformly distributed but decays exponentially, which requires correction during code development. For example, when using the mesh tally counter, the total particle path L can be divided into N equal-length segments:

$$\Delta x = \frac{L}{N}, x_i = i \Delta x \quad (11)$$

The mean survival probability within the i -th segment $[x_i, x_i + \Delta x]$ is then given by Eq. (12):

$$w_i = \frac{1}{\Delta x} \int_{x_i}^{x_i + \Delta x} e^{-\Sigma_a x} dx \quad (12)$$

and the integrated result can be expressed as Eq. (13).

In these expressions, w_i represents the expected particle weight that survives upon traversing mesh i , i.e., its contribution factor to the tally. This term can be interpreted as a "locally averaged attenuation weight," effectively introducing an exponential decay correction into the track-length estimator.

$$w_i = \frac{1}{\Delta x} \left[-\frac{1}{\Sigma_a} e^{-\Sigma_a x} \right]_{x_i}^{x_i + \Delta x} = \frac{1}{\Delta x} \cdot \frac{1}{\Sigma_a} \left(e^{-\Sigma_a x_i} - e^{-\Sigma_a (x_i + \Delta x)} \right) \quad (13)$$

It is evident that as $\Sigma_a \rightarrow 0$, $w_i \rightarrow 1$, reducing to the conventional uniform-weight tally. Conversely, as Σ_a increases, w_i shifts toward the path origin, reflecting the rapid attenuation of particles during penetration. This correction method is equally applicable to cell-based tallies.

2.3. Collision-Probability-Based Variance Reduction Technique

Given the dual role of hydrogen atoms in shielding calculations, as discussed in the research background, a bias is introduced in the simulation to control the selection probability of H-1 atoms. This approach aims to selectively suppress excessive neutron moderation and the associated absorption loss induced by hydrogen.

2.3.1. Macroscopic Cross-Section Scaling Mechanism for H-1

A user-defined H-1 retention factor $f \in (0, 1]$ is introduced:

$$\Sigma_{s,H}^b = f \cdot \Sigma_{s,H}, f \in (0, 1] \quad (14)$$

During each collision, the original scattering cross-section sampling mechanism selects an H-1 atom with a probability proportional to $\Sigma_{s,H}^H / \Sigma_s$. After applying the retention factor, the total macroscopic cross section is modified as shown in Eq. (15).

$$\Sigma_t^{orig} = \Sigma_t^b + (1 - f)\Sigma_{s,H} \quad (15)$$

The difference between the true and biased total macroscopic cross sections is defined in Eq. (16):

$$\Delta\Sigma = \Sigma_t^{orig} - \Sigma_t^b = (1 - f)\Sigma_{s,H} \quad (16)$$

The sampling probability for scattering reactions involving H-1 atoms is thus reduced to $(\Sigma_{s,H}^H / \Sigma_s) \times f$, effectively lowering the frequency of H-1 collisions and consequently decreasing the degree of neutron moderation.

To preserve the unbiasedness of the transport statistics, a compensatory adjustment is applied to the neutron track weight w , increasing it in proportion to the introduced bias.

2.3.2. Dual-Factor Weight Correction

In Monte Carlo transport, the sampled path length d follows an exponential distribution. After biasing, the ratio between the true and biased probability densities of the particle's flight distance d is given by Eq. (17):

$$W_{dist}(d) = \frac{p_{true}(d)}{p_b(d)} = \frac{\Sigma_t^{orig}}{\Sigma_t^b} e^{(\Sigma_t^{orig} - \Sigma_t^b)d} = \frac{\Sigma_t^{orig}}{\Sigma_t^b} e^{-\Delta\Sigma d} \quad (17)$$

where W_{dist} denotes the distance correction factor.

Considering the ratio between the true scattering probability of H-1 collisions and the scaled one:

$$p_i^{true} = \frac{\Sigma_i^{orig}}{\Sigma_t^{orig}}, p_i^b = \frac{\Sigma_i^b}{\Sigma_t^b} \quad (18)$$

the relationship in Eq. (19) can be derived:

$$W_{sel,i} = \frac{p_i^{true}}{p_i^b} = \frac{\Sigma_i^{orig}}{\Sigma_i^{orig}} \cdot \frac{\Sigma_i^b}{\Sigma_i^b} \quad (19)$$

where W_{sel} represents the sampling probability correction factor.

Accordingly, the total post-collision weight correction accounts for both the distance correction and the selection correction, thereby ensuring the unbiasedness of the transport results with any H-1 retention factor.

For collisions involving H-1 nuclei, the iterative update of particle weight follows Eq. (20):

$$w' = w \cdot W_{dist}(d) \cdot W_{sel,H} = w \cdot \frac{1}{f} \cdot e^{-\Delta\Sigma d} \quad (20)$$

while for collisions with non-hydrogen nuclei, the weight iteration is given by Eq. (21):

$$w' = w \cdot e^{-\Delta\Sigma d} \quad (21)$$

In mesh-tally or track-length-based estimators (MeshTally and TLE), the final scoring and counting are performed by analytically integrating with the true cross sections and multiplying by the appropriate correction factors, as shown in Eq. (22).

$$contrib_{seg} = w_{seg} \sum_r \frac{1 - e^{-\Sigma_i^{orig} l}}{\Sigma_i^{orig}} \quad (22)$$

2.4. Implementation in the Open-Source Monte Carlo Code OpenMC

The overall implementation workflow is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Program Flow of the PDF-Based Variance Reduction Implementation in OpenMC.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, numerical tests are performed to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed Local Variance Reduction (LVR) method for deep-penetration shielding problems, and to compare its improvement relative to conventional Monte Carlo simulations. The Figure of Merit (FOM) is defined as [8]:

$$FOM = \frac{1}{t \cdot \sigma^2} \quad (23)$$

where t is the computational time in seconds, and σ represents the average relative standard deviation of all tally quantities of interest within the model domain. All simulations using different methods are conducted under identical computational conditions.

3.1. Deep-Penetration Shielding Model

To verify the variance reduction performance of the developed non-analog Monte Carlo method, calculations are carried out using a two-dimensional deep-penetration model. The geometric configuration and material composition of the model are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Model geometry. Red point is the source, dark blue is water, pink is iron, and light blue is concrete.

An isotropic 4 MeV neutron source is placed at the central red origin, enclosed within a symmetric water layer measuring 400×50 cm. On the right side of the water region, a 25 cm thick iron block of equal height is positioned, while the remaining space is filled with concrete. The overall dimensions of the model in the x - y plane are 500×500 cm, and vacuum boundary conditions are applied around the concrete domain.

(a) Analog MC (b) HPB-MC (c) PLHPB-MC

Figure 3. Average flux in the central x - y slice of the geometry, from the instance simulated with three different methods.

For tallying, the two-dimensional space is divided into a 100×100 mesh grid. Fixed-source transport simulations are performed in OpenMC, with 10 batches of particles, each containing 1×10^7 histories[9]. In the path-length biasing scheme, the scattering cross section is used in place of the total cross section for flight sampling. Within H_2O , the atomic ratio of H-1 to O-16 is reduced to the empirical parameter 0.18 — which is derived from the statistical characteristics of a pre-generated deep-penetration trajectory library, considered to achieve better VR gain for water-based materials.

A flux cut-off threshold is applied for mesh cells where the neutron flux falls below ten orders of magnitude relative to the source flux.

3.2. Comparative Analysis of Simulation Results

In this section, three simulation schemes were performed on the same shielding instance: (a) the conventional analog Monte Carlo method (Analog MC), (b) the Monte Carlo method with hydrogen

collision probability biasing (HPB-MC), and (3) the Monte Carlo method with both path-length and hydrogen collision probability biasing (PLHPB-MC).

(a) Analog MC (b) HPB-MC (c) PLHPB-MC

Figure 4. Relative standard deviation in the central x-y slice of the geometry, from the instance simulated with three different methods.

Figures 3 and 4 present the calculated neutron flux distributions and the corresponding relative standard deviations, respectively. The comparison clearly demonstrates the variance reduction achieved by applying event-biased sampling strategies relative to the analog simulation.

Table I. Performance Comparison Among Different Methods.

	Analog MC	HPB-MC	PLHPB-MC
Monte Carlo Runtime(s)	1.411×10^3	2.393×10^3	1.519×10^4
Effective mesh fraction(%)	21.75	92.27	97.66
Mean relative error $\bar{\sigma}$	9.950×10^{-4}	2.460×10^{-3}	2.137×10^{-3}
Mean FOM	7.327	8.529	1.586

As shown in the figure, a significant improvement is observed after applying the biasing scheme. The neutron trajectories become noticeably longer, enhancing the particle contribution to far-field regions, while the spatial variance across mesh tallies is substantially reduced.

Table 1 presents the computational results for the three cases. In the two-dimensional model space consisting of 10,000 meshes, the fraction of meshes in which particle histories are actually detected in the current Monte Carlo simulation is defined as the “effective mesh fraction,” which is used to quantify the coverage of particle detection. It can be clearly observed that the number of effective mesh cells increases significantly after applying the biasing strategies, rising from 21.8% to over 90%. Although the simulation time of the HPB-MC case increases by 69.60%, the FOM value still improves by 16.41% due to the acquisition of more effective particle histories. When the path-length biasing is further applied on this basis, the reduction in relative error becomes less pronounced; nevertheless, the number of effective mesh cells continues to increase.

In non-analog Monte Carlo simulations employing particle event-biasing, the adjustment of particle weights and the stochastic survival mechanism across different batches often lead to significant variations in effective particle utilization, variance convergence rates, and computational time. Figure 5 presents a tracking and comparative analysis of simulation performance across particle generations.

The results indicate that, as the number of source particles increases, the Monte Carlo runtime grows approximately linearly, consistent with the scaling expectation of event statistics under parallel execution. Meanwhile, the mean relative standard deviation gradually decreases with increasing particle count, exhibiting the typical $1/N$ convergence behavior. In contrast, the FoM shows larger fluctuations at low particle counts but stabilizes once a sufficient number of particles is sampled, suggesting that the influence of statistical fluctuations on computational efficiency diminishes.

Figure 5. Scaling of the average MC run time (left), mean standard deviation (center), and FoM (right) with varying neutron populations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study proposes a local event-biased weighting method based on path length and hydrogen collision probability to address the low efficiency of Monte Carlo simulations in deep-penetration shielding calculations. The method dynamically adjusts sampling probabilities and particle weights at the trajectory level, thereby optimizing microscopic particle behavior, effectively reducing variance, and accelerating convergence.

The proposed approach has been implemented in the open-source continuous-energy Monte Carlo code OpenMC and validated through representative shielding benchmarks. The results demonstrate that the method can significantly improve statistical efficiency in deep-penetration scenarios.

In addition, this type of VR method may have potential limitations. For example, in the collision-probability biasing step, the retention factor f should not be set too small, as $1/f$ would excessively amplify the particle weight when H-1 events occur, potentially causing long-tail effects. Moreover, for different hydrogen-based shielding materials, the efficiency gain achieved when applying HPB is closely related to the choice of the retention factor, and further investigation is needed to assess the sensitivity of the results to this parameter.

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